

Teckollab:

A governance-led model for sustainable
venture building and collaboration

BridgeAI

The
Alan Turing
Institute

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A governance-led model for sustainable venture building and collaboration

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Topic overview

Teckollab is a Wiltshire-based tech studio partnering with purpose-led, ambitious startups from idea through MVP to market leadership. This case study explores how **Teckollab** is building a governance-led collaboration framework for sustainable venture building, supported by AI. The framework is designed to address risks faced by early-stage tech company founders when entering co-creation or co-selling partnerships, including uncertainties around intellectual property, ownership, and division of labour – all while enabling capital-efficient growth. Participation in Bridge AI – The Turing Way Practitioners Hub has helped Teckollab refine this governance-led model and strengthen the best practices, such as documentation standards, that underpin responsible collaboration for co-creation and co-selling.

Navigating collaboration as an early-stage venture

Many early-stage founders actively avoid collaboration despite its potential benefits,” says Aariffa Hajamaideen, founder of Teckollab and a Turing Way Practitioners Hub Expert-in-Residence. “That’s because of past experiences or fears around intellectual property loss and unclear ownership boundaries. This hesitation can limit a startup’s opportunities for growth or waste capital through overinvestment in internal builds.”

And when companies do collaborate – with corporate partners, expert consultants, investors, researcher institutes or delivery partners – it is often out of necessity, before formal, thought-through governance structures are in place.

In this context, co-creation involves partners working together to design and build solutions while maintaining clearly defined ownership of their respective contributions – for example, a climate-focused startup collaborating with a research group and an industry organisation to jointly develop an AI-based solution to an environmental challenge. Co-selling, meanwhile, allows partners to bring products to market via each other’s established networks, such as a health innovator offering its solution through partnerships with healthcare providers that can introduce it to hospitals already within their ecosystems.

Collaboration of this type carries risks including:

- intellectual property ambiguities
- power imbalances in negotiations
- differing levels of expertise among partners
- licensing incompatibilities
- AI and data ownership uncertainty
- post-termination access disputes

How it works: Four pillars of governance-led collaboration

Image credit: Teckollab, shared under CC-BY 4.0 licence

Teckollab takes a layered, governance-first approach to collaboration. Rather than offering a one-size-fits-all solution, Teckollab combines education, governance design, reusable technical foundations, and ecosystem partnerships.

1. Knowledge and founder education

Sustainable collaboration starts with awareness. Through Teckollab's blog, ***Beyond Launch: The Scaling Series***, the company provides founders with practical education on scalability, governance and IP risks commonly encountered from pre-seed to Series A funding rounds. This includes real-world scenarios, collaboration breakdown patterns, and commercially grounded responses.

The series is being strengthened with practical guidelines, standards and frameworks informed by insights gathered through the Practitioners Hub. The aim is to reduce avoidable risk by equipping founders with clearer mental models before they enter complex partnerships.

Governance Framework & Collaboration Design

Currently human-led, supported by AI-enabled tools that enhance analysis and documentation without replacing human judgement.

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2. Governance framework and collaboration design

At the core of Teckollab's work is a domain-agnostic governance framework used to design collaboration architectures and governance roadmaps tailored to each venture.

This includes:

- clear IP classification and ownership boundaries
- defined commercial rights and responsibilities
- access controls and decision rights
- collaboration guardrails aligned to stage and risk profile.

The framework is currently human-led, supported by AI-enabled tools that enhance analysis, documentation and processing. AI acts as an enabler, improving efficiency and consistency, but not replacing human judgment. Over time, the goal is to minimise manual intervention without compromising contextual oversight, accountability or governance integrity.

3. Reusable infrastructure and interoperability foundations

To support capital-efficient venture building, Teckollab develops domain-agnostic infrastructure patterns and reusable design and code components that embed governance principles by default.

This includes:

- modular architectural patterns
- interoperability-ready integrations
- agentic AI orchestration models
- clear separation between proprietary and shared layers.

These patterns are first integrated and validated within Teckollab's internal products and processes before extended to live platforms. This staged approach helps de-risk uncertainty and materially reduce development cycles without compromising ownership or control.

StepZero: community collaboration

StepZero is a free sustainability action platform for UK SMEs, built by Teckollab to help businesses take actionable steps towards net zero. It was developed as an in-house venture/product where governance and infrastructure patterns were tested before being extended to collaboration partners.

The platform was built combining deep community collaboration with meticulous execution, bringing together community partnerships, credible UK sustainability frameworks and user-centred design within a governance-first development process. StepZero demonstrates how Teckollab's reusable infrastructure and collaboration principles translate into a working product designed for long-term impact.

Teckollab has published an **eight-part case study documenting how the team built a sustainability platform for UK SMEs**, from discovery through to launch.

Teckollab's agentic AI architecture prototype for vector search.
Image credit: Teckollab, shared under CC-BY 4.0 licence

AI in practice: how Teckollab's agentic AI frameworks support venture building

Teckollab's agentic AI frameworks are built on a modern web stack: React/Next.js, Node.js, PostgreSQL with pgvector for vector search and embeddings storage. The frameworks follow a template-first approach: core capabilities are developed as reusable components and extended through custom implementations for each venture.

The broader toolkit spans design, architecture and development: Microsoft 365, Google Workspace, Figma, Miro, Claude Code, GitHub Copilot, and in-house AI agents. We select what is relevant for each venture and offering.

Current framework capabilities include:

- retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) for document analysis
- natural language data interrogation
- integration orchestration via Node.js, with human-led oversight for quality and governance
- confidence-calibrated recommendations and automated handoffs on the development roadmap
- AI-powered design and architecture tooling across documentation, UX and governance workflows

The technology choices are deliberate. Having evaluated dedicated orchestration tools and standalone vector databases, Teckollab chose Node.js and PostgreSQL with pgvector for the combination of capability and simplicity appropriate for pre-seed to seed stage ventures. Running AI frameworks on the same full-stack platform avoids premature hiring of AI engineers or specialists, keeping teams lean and focused. As ventures mature, individual components can be scaled or replaced without significant rework, ensuring the architecture serves founders today without constraining them tomorrow.

Some elements are currently tested in pilot deployments, including semantic search and RAG with hybrid manual and automated orchestration. Further work is underway in the coming months to progress towards fully automated orchestration, ready for scaled deployment.

Measurable impact on venture building

The maturing frameworks have delivered measurable improvements across Teckollab's operations:

- Product build times compressed from approximately six months (earliest ventures) to six to eight weeks (recent builds).
- Venture capacity expanded by approximately five times, supported by a single venture architect across a combination of full builds, architecture advisory, and framework integration services.
- AI capabilities such as document analysis and intelligent recommendations delivered as reusable components, removing the need for dedicated AI engineering resource within each venture.

Guardrails and responsible innovation

Responsible innovation is embedded across both the collaboration and development layers. At the architecture level, governance frameworks and guardrails are maintained through Miro, Figma, and Microsoft/Google documentation tooling, supported by custom-configured GPT and Claude agents. These tools support collaborative governance design across ventures and partners.

At the framework level, core governance principles are built into the full-stack architecture:

- IP classification boundaries that clearly separate proprietary and shared components.
- Data governance standards applied from the earliest stages of venture creation.
- Stage-appropriate governance that scales with the venture rather than imposing premature complexity.

Additional custom guardrails and governance principles can be developed on top of the framework, tailored to each venture's domain, regulatory context and collaboration requirements. This layered approach ensures that foundational responsible practices are inherited by default, while preserving the flexibility for ventures to extend governance as they mature.

Extending across the ecosystem

Teckollab is now developing a licensing model to extend these frameworks beyond its own portfolio. Independent ventures and ecosystem partners will be able to adopt the same agentic AI capabilities, with the governance guardrails inspired through the Practitioners Hub embedded by default.

4. Partnership-led ecosystem support

Governance frameworks do not replace specialist expertise. Teckollab works through a partnership network spanning legal, investment, finance and regulatory expertise to ensure founders receive appropriate, stage-aligned support. Teckollab's role is to structure and clarify collaboration boundaries, and not to substitute professional advisory services.

Teckollab prioritises partnership-led growth, recognising that sustainable venture building depends on coordinated expertise rather than centralised control. In practice, Teckollab's partnership ecosystem currently spans community partners supporting founder engagement and venture development, innovation bodies including Innovate UK, and the Alan Turing Institute Practitioners Hub for responsible innovation practices. Additional specialist expertise is accessed through community-referred partners as needed. These partnerships are activated based on venture stage and need, rather than maintained as fixed arrangements, keeping the model lean and relevant. The founders that Teckollab works with also form part of this ecosystem, contributing domain expertise, community relationships, and market insight that strengthen the network for future ventures.

Teckollab is also extending its offering to community partners and incorporating complementary partner services into its own, creating a more integrated ecosystem experience. This will be rolled out in the coming weeks.

Expert perspectives: IP and open collaboration

As part of the Practitioners Hub case study production process, Aariffa invited an IP lawyer and a research IT specialist to expand on the risks and challenges surrounding collaboration for founders in the tech space, to provide expert evidence to support the development of their proposed solution.

One recurring issue identified by the experts is early-stage informality. Natalie Knight-Wickens, a corporate and commercial partner at the law firm Spencer West, observes: "The top clauses that are consistently overlooked are who actually owns the IP, and who has a licence to use it. There's often a 'we'll sort it out later' approach at the beginning. But it's usually at the end that the lack of clarity becomes expensive and problematic." In practice, clear ownership demarcation and licensing arrangements are typically more sustainable.

Natalie adds: "In those early negotiations, there can also be a real imbalance of power – especially where founders don't have access to specialist legal advice. That's when risks around ownership and licensing can easily become embedded without people fully realising it." She also emphasises that founders often overlook what happens when collaborations end – including post-termination rights of use, scope of licences and exclusivity provisions – which can materially affect future commercialisation options.

From an open source and research IT perspective, Rowan Wilson, Head of Research Computing and Support Services at the University of Oxford, highlights record-keeping and licence compatibility risks. “People often assume ‘open’ means no conditions whatsoever,” says Rowan. “They adopt components without really thinking through the inbound licences, or whether what they’ve produced is something they can legally distribute. And often they haven’t kept adequate records of what went into the development process.”

He adds: “In projects with multiple contributors, there’s usually a decision to make between an assignment model, where contributors assign ownership to a central entity, and a contributor licence model, where they retain ownership but license their contributions under agreed terms. That choice has long-term consequences for commercialisation and flexibility.”

Reflecting on the additional complexity of the AI era, Rowan says: “In the AI space, intellectual property rights around data are not as settled as they are in software. Code feels more established, whereas data – especially model training data – is more problematic.”

These insights have strengthened Teckollab’s commitment to responsible innovation with stage-aligned governance clarity and documentation standards. Aariffa adds: “The discussion with the external experts also brought to light the importance of neutral or a public body backing collaborative ecosystems. Rowan referenced government-supported university collaboration frameworks as an example of a structured, trusted governance model that can mitigate asymmetry and encourage fairness.”

Next steps: Refining governance through ecosystem engagement

The next phase of Teckollab’s work involves deepening and refining its governance-led collaboration framework. The focus is on strengthening the underlying architecture by testing and adapting its features and principles across different venture contexts through our partnership network. A key priority is exploring forms of public or institutional backing that could help ensure neutrality and foster broader ecosystem trust.

Alongside this, the team is developing clearer, founder-friendly collaboration guardrails to support confident collaboration and tech integration decisions. This includes continuing to engage with the wider ecosystem of legal, research, innovation and investment stakeholders. The longer-term ambition is to embed governance thinking earlier in venture formation, reducing avoidable collaboration risk and enabling sustainable, partnership-led growth.

Reflections on *The Turing Way* Practitioners Hub

“The Turing Way Practitioners Hub gave us the space to mature our thinking around interoperability, governance and responsible collaboration. It helped shape how we document systems, share knowledge, and design for multi-partner environments. Most importantly, it reinforced our belief that governance should come before automation when building platforms intended for collaboration.”

Aariffa Hajamaideen,
Founder of Teckollab

Key takeaways

- Early-stage founders benefit from structured collaboration with external organisations, yet concerns around IP and data can hold them back. Clear governance helps founders engage in partnerships with confidence rather than caution.
- Governance-first design can prevent expensive disputes and protect founder control by addressing potential issues at the outset. Moreover, robust governance should be in place before adding features such as automation.
- Open source lowers barriers to innovation but can introduce licence, documentation and strategic trade-offs. AI, meanwhile, can introduce additional complexity around training data rights.
- Designing for ownership and trust is essential when your product is based on collaboration and partnership-led growth.
- Interoperability depends as much on documentation, workflows and shared understanding as it does on technical integrations.
- Reusable infrastructure and modular development frameworks are critical to balancing pace and agility.
- Neutral or public body supported governance frameworks may help foster trust and support balanced collaboration.

Contributors and acknowledgements

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This case study is published under ***The Turing Way Practitioners Hub*** 2025–26 Cohort – case study series. The Practitioners Hub is ***The Turing Way*** project that works with experts from partnering organisations to promote data science best practices. In 2025, The Turing Way team welcomed **Aariffa Hajamaideen and Umesh Kathirvel from Teckollab** as Experts-in-Residence to discuss and share their implementation approaches to data science and AI, as well as build additional skills around best practices in responsible, ethical, and collaborative working. We thank them for leading the development of this case study.

Innovate UK BridgeAI empowers UK businesses in high-growth sectors, driving productivity and economic growth through the adoption of Artificial Intelligence. We bridge the gap between developers and end-users, fostering user-driven AI technologies.

With a focus on ethics, transparency, and data privacy, we aim to build trust and confidence in the development of AI solutions. Strengthening AI leadership, supporting workforces, and promoting responsible innovation, BridgeAI shapes a collaborative and AI-enabled future.

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The Turing Way Practitioners Hub's 2025–26 Cohort was co-delivered by **Arielle Bennett**, Senior Researcher – Open Source Practices and Dr Ann Borda, Senior Research Community Manager. **Stuart Gillespie** is the technical writer for this case study, and others in the series. **Léllé Demertzi** is the Research Project Manager and **Denise Bianco** is the Case Study Liaison for this case study.

The Turing Way Practitioners Hub, designed and launched in 2023 by Dr Malvika Sharan, aims to accelerate the adoption of best practices. Through a six-month cohort-based program, the Hub facilitates knowledge sharing, skill exchange, case study co-creation, and the adoption of open science practices. It also fosters a network of 'Experts in Residence' across partnering organisations.

For any comments, questions or collaboration with *The Turing Way*, please email: theturingway@gmail.com

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